

Improvement of Fiber/Matrix Interface by Using Epoxy/silica Nano-hybrid

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SUMMARY: It was expected that the performance of matrix and interfacial behavior of fiber/matrix could be improved by using organic substance and organic-inorganic nano hybrid for polymer based composites. In this paper, the organic-inorganic nano hybrid was created and used as a middle layer for the interface between reinforcements and matrix. The single glass fiber was treated with the epoxy/silica hybrid sol innovated by the sol-gel process, and it was then embedded into epoxy resin in order to fabricate single fiber composite (SFC) specimens with a middle layer of nano hybrid. The interfacial behavior of fiber/matrix with and/or without the middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid for SFC was investigated. Furthermore, the different reinforcements such as short fibers and fabrics were also used to see the effect of nano hybrid as a middle layer on these practical materials. As a result, it indicated that the interfacial behavior of glass fiber/epoxy resin could be improved by introducing the middle layer of epoxy/silica nano hybrid.

KEYWORDS: Organic-inorganic nano-composite, SFC, Interface, Glass fiber

INTRODUCTION

Detailed knowledge of macroscopic fracture for fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) depends on the properties of fiber, matrix and fiber/matrix interface. Generally, the interface between fiber and matrix is a weak place of mechanical behavior. So, the reinforcements in composite materials are commonly treated by some surface agent for improvement of the adhesion between reinforcements and polymer matrix [1-5]. Many surface agents for glass reinforcements have been developed, and many efforts are being continued in order to improve interfacial characteristics of fiber/matrix in the FRP. However, there is a limit for the improvement of the interface characteristics by the traditional method and a new approach should be necessary. On the other hand, the organic-inorganic hybrid in a scale of nanometers is a new class of materials that may offer a variety of advantage, such as mechanical, optical electrical and thermal properties. So such nanohybrid materials are used wide for new electronic and optical materials, such as contact lenses [6], high refraction index materials [7], optical devices [8], photo chromic materials [9], wave guide materials [10] and biomaterials [11]. Because an inorganic element coexists with the organic element, the adhesive property to the organic substance and/or the inorganic substance will be improved. This may be extremely effective for composite materials. In this paper, interfacial behavior of fiber/matrix based on organic-inorganic hybrid was investigated. The single glass fiber was treated with the epoxy /silica hybrid sol innovated by the sol-gel process.

Single fiber composite (SFC) specimens were fabricated by embedding the single fiber with a middle layer of the epoxy/silica hybrid sol into an epoxy resin. Then the interfacial behavior of fiber/ matrix with and/or without the epoxy/silica hybrid was investigated. And, for the practical use and comparison, several reinforcements such as glass chopped strands and glass fabric were used. The concept of nano hybrid middle layer for improving the interfacial behavior was shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 The concept of nano hybrid middle layer

Materials and EXPERIMENTAL

1. Preparation of epoxy/silica sol

The materials used in this study were commercial ones of reagent grade chemicals. Matrix is a liquid diglycidyl ether of bisphenol type A epoxy resin (Epikote 828). The curing agent used was a tetraethylenepentamine, and the alkoxy silane used was 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy silane. The epoxy/silica hybrid sols were prepared based on Ochi's method [12], but the process and some conditions were modified. The prescribed amount of 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy silane was added to Epikote 828 by stirring at 80°C for 20min. Then 1phr of H₂O was added and stirred vigorously to obtain homogeneous solution. In addition, a stoichiometric amount of curing agent for epoxy matrix was added at 50°C and then the mixtures were stirred to obtain transparent sol.

2. Fabrication of single fiber composite (SFC)

The fiber used for SFC specimens was an E-glass continuous fiber of 13μm (Asahi Fiber Glass Co. Ltd.), and its surface was treated by amino silane. The SFC specimens were fabricated by embedding a single fiber with a middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol, into an epoxy resin. A frame with the thickness of 0.7mm was made on an aluminum plate and a single glass filament was pre-stressed in tension of about 1g. The compounds were cured at 50°C for 80 min, 60°C for 4h, and 100°C for 2h. After that the plate was allowed to cool down slowly to room temperature. The specimens were fabricated according to the standard of JIS K7113-1995, and the dimension and shape of specimen are shown in Fig.2. In order to compare their interface behavior, the specimens with a glass fiber but without the middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol were also fabricated by the same procedures as above. Here, the SFC specimen with the middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid is abbreviated to EGH, and the one without the middle phase is abbreviated to EG, respectively.

3. Measurement of the thickness of middle layer

The weight of naked glass fibers was measured. Then, the glass fibers were treated with epoxy/silica hybrid sol, and after drying the fibers their weight was measured again. The thickness of the middle layer was calculated according to the weight change and the density of epoxy/silica hybrid sol.

4. Fragmentation test and measurement of AE signals

The tensile tests for single fibers were conducted in a CATY-500BH machine (YoneKura) with fiber gage length of 20mm. The crosshead speed was 0.3mm/min.

The fragmentation tests of SFC specimens were conducted in an Instron type machine (4466). The acoustic emission signals were monitored during the tensile process and the AE measuring system (Shimazu SAE1000) was used. Two AE sensors with a wide range of frequency (about 1 MHz) were attached to the SFC specimen in two locations at a distance of 40mm to locate the AE signals and to eliminate noise (Fig. 2). AE signals detected by two sensors were amplified by the preamplifier, passed through a high pass filter of 10kHz and a low pass filter of 1000kHz to remove noise, and then amplified again by the main amplifier to 80dB. The threshold voltage was set at 0.05mV (34dB).

The microscopic observation of failures, such as fiber break, and matrix cracking within the specimen were conducted by using polarized microscope (Olympus Optical Co., Ltd., GX51) after fragmentation test. The number of fiber breakages was counted, which was used for the calculation of shear strength.

Figure.2 The geometry of a specimen

5. SEM observation of chopped glass strands

The chopped glass strands (length: 6mm, Asahi Fiber Glass Co. Ltd.) were used as the reinforcement for epoxy resin to confirm the difference of the interfacial behavior with and/or without middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol. The chopped glass strands with middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol were prepared by passing the strands through the hybrid sol and then by embedding them in epoxy resin. After tensile fracture, their difference in interfacial behavior was observed by the fractographs of the cross section (SEM, Nikon ESEM-2700).

6. Peeling test

The difference of interfacial behavior with and/or without middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol was compared by a peeling test. Here, glass fabric was used as the reinforcement; the epoxy resin was used as a matrix; and 180° peeling strength was measured as shown in Fig.3 by the peeling test at peeling speed 3mm/min. The specimens for peeling test were fabricated by painting epoxy/silica sol on one side of the glass fabric and then pouring epoxy resin into the painted glass fabric. The dimension of the specimen for epoxy bulk was of width 20mm, length 200mm, and thickness 2mm, while for the glass fabric was of width 30mm and length 350mm in order to avoid fraying of the edges of glass fabric. As a comparison, the specimens without middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol

for glass fabric were also fabricated by the same procedures as above.

Figure 3. The schematic representation of the peeling test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile strength and fracture elongation of single glass fibers were obtained by the single fiber tensile test, and their results were shown in Table 1.

Although the thickness of middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol coated on the single glass fiber was 3-5 μ m according to the weight changes, for the SFC composites where the fibers were embedded into the epoxy resin, the interface layer between epoxy/silica and epoxy resin may not exist obviously because epoxy resin in liquid was poured into epoxy/silica hybrid sol state and their dissolution and reaction may occurs each other in the curing process.

Table 1 Tensile strength and fracture elongation of single fibers

Tensile strength GPa	Standard deviation of tensile strength GPa	Fracture longation %	Standard deviation of fracture elongation %
2.62	0.131	3.67	0.23

1. Comparison with SFCs for interface

AE activity patterns can be used to identify failure process. Fig. 4(a), (b) and (c) shows the stress-elongation curves and AE activity patterns for the bulk of epoxy resin, SFC specimens of EG without middle layer, and SFC specimens of ENG with middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol, respectively. In the stress-elongation of each specimen, regardless of the existence of embedding single fiber, the elasticity coefficient of material during the early deformation action was almost the same. However, the difference due to embedding single fiber was observed obviously at the high load level near the fracture.

Only few AE signals were measured for the bulk specimen [Fig.4 (a)], while many AE signals were detected in SFC specimens. Observing AE occurrence in SFCs the initial AE signal occurred near the transition point from liner to non-liner stress-elongation behavior, and many AE signals were concentrated just before the fracture of the specimens.

Compared AE signals measured in SFC specimens with and/or without middle layer, it was found that:

1. the initial AE signal in ENG-SFC specimens occurred at higher applied stress than in EG-SFC.

2.the number of AE events in EGH-SFC (Fig. 4(c)) is larger than that in EG-SFC (Fig. 4(b)) . Because the total number of AE events corresponded to the number of fiber breakages as reported [15,16], the above AE characteristics indicate the improvement of the interfacial behavior at the interface of fiber/matrix in EGH-SFC due to introduction of middle layer.

(a) Epoxy resin bulk

(b) EG-SFC

(c) EGH-SFC

Fig.4. Relationships between stress and elongation, AE event count rate and time in epoxy bulk and SFCs

Figure 5 shows polarized microfractographs at a fiber breakage for SFC specimens. The debonding failure at the interface of fiber/matrix was observed, but there was no cracking for the EG-SFC without middle layer (Fig. 5(a)). On the other hand, for the EGH-SFC specimen with middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid sol a large disk-shaped matrix crack at the fiber breakage point was observed. This also indicates that the interface due to epoxy/silica hybrid sol treatment was improved.

(a) EG-SFC

(b) EGH-SFC

Fig.5. Polarized microfractographs at a fiber breakage in SFCs.

Microfractographs of the cross section for SFC specimen were shown in Figure 6 . For EG-SFC (Fig.6(a)) without epoxy/silica hybrid sol treatment, the crack seems propagate fast and fractured face was flat and presents a radial pattern in the whole cross section. On the other hand, for the EGH-SFC specimens, two parts of radial pattern were observed. The central part may accompany with fiber break. The treatment of the glass fiber with the epoxy/silica hybrid sol does have resulted in the changes of the fractographs.

(a) EG-SFC

(b) EGH-sfc

Fig.6 Microphotograph of the cross section in SFCs

In The following formula based on the fiber fragment length was used to evaluate interfacial shear strength in SFC specimens [13,14].

$$t = \frac{ds_f}{2l_m} K$$

Here , d :diameter of fiber

s_f : tensile strength of fiber

l_m : mean fiber fragment length

K : modification coefficient (0.75)

In other words, the fiber breakage point was counted, and then the interfacial shear strength was evaluated by this fragmentation test. The results are shown in Table 2. Here, the silica weight content in the hybrid sol for EGH-SFC specimens was 3.93%. According to the results of interfacial shear strength, it is understood that the interfacial shear strength in EGH-SFC with epoxy/silica hybrid sol treatment is about two times as large as that in EG-SFC without the hybrid sol treatment.

Table 2. Mean fragment lengths and interfacial shear strength

Sample code	Mean number of fiber segments	Mean fragment Length (mm)	Interfacial shear Strength (MPa)
EG-SFC	6.3	3.17	3.89
EGH-SFC	11.5	1.74	7.05

Fig.7 The relationship between shear strength and silica content of hybrids in SFCs

For EGH-SFC specimens, the effect of silica content of epoxy/silica hybrid on interfacial shear strength was investigated. The relationship between shear strength and the silica content of hybrid sol is shown in Fig .7. The maximum value of the interfacial shear strength was observed at 3.93wt% of the silica content and after that the interfacial shear strength decreased. This may result from the increment of brittleness due to the excess amount of the silica network that may cause the adhesion layer brittle and then lead to the decrement of interfacial shear strength [12].

2. Comparison in short fiber and textile fabric

The effect with or without a middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid on the interface behavior was investigated in short fibers and textile fabric. The microfractograph for chopped strand glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin was shown in Fig. 8. When the chopped strand glass fiber was not coated by middle layer (Fig. 8 (a)), almost no epoxy resin could be observed at the surface of the glass fiber. This may resulted from the weak adhesion between the glass fiber/matrix. On the other hand, when the glass fiber was coated by a middle layer of epoxy/silica hybrid (Fig. 8 (b)) the cohesive fracture with a hackle pattern in the epoxy resin was observed. Since the hackle pattern usually occurs for a strong adhesion it indicated the adhesion between fiber and matrix may be high.

Fig.8 Microphotographs of the cross section in short glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites.

Fig.9. The peeling strength for glass fiber fabric composites.

In order to investigate the effect of the middle phase on interface for the practical composites, the glass fiber fabric reinforced epoxy resin was fabricated and the 180° peeling tests were conducted. The result of the peeling tests is shown in Fig.9. In this figure, it is shown that the peeling load

between glass fiber fabric and epoxy resin with the epoxy/silica middle layer, is about 10% higher than that without the epoxy/silica middle layer.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new approach to improvement of interfacial behavior for composites was proposed by using organic-inorganic nano-hybrid as a middle layer. Several typical reinforcements such as continuous glass fiber, chopped strand glass fiber and glass fabric were treated by epoxy /silica nano hybrid and a middle layer between reinforcement of glass fibers and the matrix of epoxy resin was created. The composites with this nano-hybrid middle layer for reinforcements were fabricated. Then the interfacial behavior with and/or without the nano hybrid middle layer was investigated and compared by the fragmentation test with simultaneous AE measurements, peeling tests and SEM observation. It was found that the interfacial behavior between glass fiber and epoxy resin could be improved greatly by introducing the middle layer of epoxy/silica nano hybrid. It was confident that the concept of using organic-inorganic hybrid as a middle layer between reinforcements and matrix would be one of effective approaches for improvement of the interfacial behavior in composites.

REFERENCES

1. B. Gao, J.-K. Kim, and C. K. Y. Leung, *Composites Science and Technology*, 63(2003)883.
2. M. Tanoglu, S. H. McKnight, G. R. Palmese and J. W. Gillespie Jr , *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 18(1998) 431.
3. J. M. L. Reis and A. J. M. Ferreira , *Polymer Testing*, 22(2003) 149.
4. S. M. Clifford, C. I. C. Manger and T. W. Clyne , *Composite Structures*, 57(2002) 59.
5. R. W. Venderbosch, T. Peijst, H. E. H. Meijer and P. L. Lemstra, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 27(1996) 895.
6. G. Philipp and H. Schmidt, *J. Non-Crystalline solids*, 63(1984)283.
7. Padimitrakopoulos, P. isniecki, and D. Bhagwagar, *Chem. Mater.*, 9(1997) 2928.
8. G. Cartenuto, Y. S. Her, and E. Matijevic, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 35(1996) 2929.
9. J. Biteau, F. Chaput, K. Lahlil, J. P. Boilot, G. M. Tsivgoulis, J. M. Lehn, B. Drracq, C. Marois, and Y. Levy, *Chem, Mat*, 10, (1998) 1945.
10. M. Yoshida and P. N. Prasad, *Chem. Mat.*, 8, 235(1996)235.
11. J. M. Yang, C. H. Lu, Y. G., C. H. Shih, *J. Biomed Mater Res. (Appl Biomaterial)* 38 (1997) 143.
12. M. Ochi, R. Takahashi, A. Terauchi, *Polymer*, 42(2001) 5151.
13. A. N. Netravail, Z-F. Li, W. Sachse and H. F. Wu, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 26(1991) 6631.
14. P. W. R. Beaumont and P. Anstice, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 15(1980)2619.
15. A. Netravail, Z-F. Li, W. Sachse and H. F. Wu, *J. Mater. Sci.*, 26(1991) 6631.
16. Q.-Q. Ni, E. Jine, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 56(1997)779.